

Editorial—How to write a winning paper

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The *Cambodian Journal of Natural History* was launched in 2008 to help address the critical need for information on the status, use and management of the biodiversity of Cambodia. Besides publishing and distributing peer-reviewed papers in a free, open-access forum, this journal also aims to strengthen the writing skills of Cambodian conservation researchers and managers.

In the last issue (Volume 2012, number 1), one of us (MF) offered some personal advice to would-be writers, based on long experience as both an author and an editor. Here, we thought it would be helpful to provide some more detailed advice on how to construct a winning scientific article and how to avoid some common pitfalls.

The sections outlined below follow the structure of full papers in most scientific journals, including the *Cambodian Journal of Natural History*. When preparing a manuscript, however, you should always read and heed the journal's own Instructions for Contributors (the instructions for this journal can be found at the back of this issue). It is also a good idea to look at recent issues of the journal to gain a feel for its style and gauge whether it will suit your material.

Title

This is the hook to capture your readers, and should be fairly short—ideally not more than 10 words. The title should give an honest indication of the contents of the paper, but does not need to be dry and dull. For example, the title “Is fire good for forests?” could arouse more interest than “A study of the impacts of anthropogenic burning on the composition of plants in dry forests”. Some authors like to include their principal aim or conclusion in the title, e.g. “First census of white-shouldered ibis *Pseudibis davisoni* reveals roost-site mismatch with Cambodia's protected areas”.

Authors

Will you be the only author of the paper, or should there be one or more coauthors? It is entirely up to you to decide, but a useful rule of thumb is that every coauthor

ought to have made at least two of the following four contributions:-

- *Planning/facilitating the research*: e.g. figuring out how to collect data, identifying the research questions, securing grants to fund the work, providing essential equipment, identifying the research site.
- *Collecting data*: e.g. interviewing villagers, setting camera traps, conducting a literature review, identifying species.
- *Analysing data*: e.g. statistical and graphical analysis, providing new insights from the results.
- *Writing the paper*: e.g. writing some sections of the manuscript, giving extensive comments on early drafts.

For the *Cambodian Journal of Natural History*, we urge all foreign authors to invite their Cambodian counterparts and assistants to be coauthors.

There is practically no limit on the number of people who can coauthor a paper—the current record being 2,926 authors for one paper on the Large Hadron Collider! However, it is important that every author agrees to their name being included. Every coauthor should have a chance to review successive drafts of the paper and approve the final version.

Deciding the order in which names are presented can be difficult. We recommend: (i) The person who has done the most work in writing the paper should be the First Author (the first name in the list); (ii) If another person has done a large share of the writing, they can be the second name in the list; (iii) Most coauthors can then be listed in alphabetical order, using their family names; (iii) If there are a lot of coauthors it is a common practice for the most senior member (e.g. the professor or head of the department) to be placed last. However, decisions about authorship and the order of names should be made by the First Author in consultation with the other authors.

The ‘Corresponding Author’ is the person to whom questions or requests should be directed by readers. This is usually the First Author, but can be one of the coauthors, by mutual consent.

Abstract (Summary)

Apart from the title, most people read only the Abstract. It must therefore be understandable on its own. The Abstract helps readers to decide whether to read the entire article and, more importantly, tells them your main findings.

A recommended structure for the Abstract is as follows (but do not include subheadings): *Background*: A simple opening sentence to give the context of your study; *Aims*: One or two sentences giving the purpose of the work; *Methods*: One or two sentences explaining what you did; *Results*: One or two sentences to summarise your main findings; *Conclusions*: One sentence giving the most important consequences or implications of the work, e.g. What do the results mean? How will they be used? What recommendations are you making as a result of this work?

The Abstract should not contain any references or abbreviations. Most journals set a strict word limit for abstracts. The *Cambodian Journal of Natural History* permits a maximum of 250 words.

Although the Abstract appears at the start, this is usually the last section to be written. We suggest you re-read your entire paper from start to finish and then draft the Abstract without looking back at the text. Try to avoid copying entire sentences—you are liable to include too much information, or too little.

Keywords

Keywords are used by database search engines to help people locate articles containing subjects of interest to them. Most journals set a maximum of eight keywords, but check the Instructions for Contributors for guidance.

Here are some suggestions for picking keywords:

- If your paper focuses on a particular region, habitat, species or community, use that as a keyword e.g. Annamite Mountains, mangroves, tiger, dipterocarps, Stung Treng.
- Consider using your materials or techniques e.g. camera-trapping, electron microscope, animal tracks, Participatory Land Use Planning, interviews.
- If they were discussed in your paper, include important issues or phenomena e.g. climate change, pollution, habitat fragmentation, fisheries, Forestry Law.
- If covered in your Discussion, refer to possible future applications or recommendations e.g. sustainable harvesting, habitat restoration, species conservation, payments for environmental services, training.

Introduction

The purpose of the Introduction is to present the subject of your work and place it in the context of what is already known about this topic. Write this section in the past or present tense, *not* in the future tense (avoid expressions such as “This study will examine...”).

The first and last paragraphs of your Introduction are the most important. First, you must provide some context and background for your work, referring to the work of others as appropriate. Try to avoid mentioning your study organism and study location in the first paragraph. The Introduction is meant to introduce the reader to your research, not summarise and evaluate everything that has ever been written on the subject.

Depending on the journal you are submitting to, you should consider whether the audience is likely to be general or specialised. For example, if you submit an article on Asian elephants to the *Cambodian Journal of Natural History* you ought to provide more background information on elephants than if you submit it to *Gajah* (the journal of the IUCN/SSC Asian Elephant Specialist Group).

You also need to consider whether to use the passive or active voice in your article. For example, the *passive voice* would say “the work was carried out” and “it was observed that...”, whereas the *active voice* would say “I carried out the work” or “we observed that...” (use the singular ‘I’ if you are the only author). Whichever style you choose, be consistent throughout your article. We recommend you use the active voice.

The final paragraph or last few sentences (depending on the length of the Introduction) should contain your research questions or the aims of your work.

Methods

This is often the easiest section to write and many authors prefer to write this section first.

The Methods should provide a clear description of how you carried out your study. A good way to approach this section is to imagine that one of the readers wants to replicate your study. Your methods must be sufficiently clear for them to repeat your study accurately, without asking you for further information. This section also allows other researchers to evaluate your methodology and judge whether your conclusions are valid.

Methods sections are normally fairly short and do not require subsection headings. (As a general rule, use subsections only if the Methods section is longer than five paragraphs). Your Methods should contain a thor-

ough description of the study design and methodology, including the location and any equipment used. Provide the make and manufacturer of the equipment if it is a specialised item that is not in common use—there is no need to provide the model and manufacturer of common equipment such as binoculars, tape measures, or hand-held global positioning systems. If any of your methods have been fully described in a previous, readily available publication (yours or someone else's), you can cite that instead of describing the procedure again.

It is very important to state *when* your work was carried out and *where*. If your study took place in the field, provide a map to show the location. A written description of the study area is also warranted if your work was carried out in the field e.g. vegetation types, climate, altitude, topography, soils, local human populations, or other matters. This content will depend on what is relevant to the focus of your article. For example, if your paper is about community fisheries, you ought to provide more details about the rivers or lakes in your study area, the number and distribution of people involved in fishing, and the names of the villages, communes and districts. Use the *past tense* when describing the situation particular to the time when your work was carried out (e.g. “during our study, mean rainfall was 112 mm per month”; “the village had 423 residents”). If describing the general, ongoing situation in your study area, you can use the *present tense* (e.g. “mean annual rainfall in Phnom Penh is 1,635 mm per year”; “Ta Sal Commune is in Aoral District”).

The Methods section must contain a full description of any statistical or modelling methods used, including equations. There is no need to say your data were written in notebooks or entered into a spreadsheet, but if you used a statistical package to analyse your data, you should explain which one (including version and the company concerned); e.g. R, Minitab, SPSS.

The amount of information you should give about a method will depend on how well known the technique is. For well-known methods, such as camera-trapping, the name of the method and one or two references (citations) will generally suffice. Completely new methods will require a more detailed description.

Results

The function of this section is simply to summarise trends in your own data without any interpretation or discussion. All statements must be directly based on your data, and this section should not contain references to the literature.

The results of statistical tests (if used) can be presented in parentheses after a verbal description: e.g. “fruit size was significantly greater in trees growing alone ($t = 3.65$, $df = 2$, $P < 0.05$).”

The Results section typically contains tables and figures (graphs, drawings, photographs, maps) to present the data. Avoid unnecessary duplication between the text, figures and tables: the tables and figures contain the details whereas the text presents a summary of the findings. Whenever possible, use graphs instead of tables because relationships between numbers are more easily grasped when presented graphically.

When using tables: (i) Avoid repeating data in a table if it is depicted in a graph, or *vice versa*; (ii) It is easier to compare numbers by reading down a column rather than across a row, so list data you wish your reader to compare in vertical form; (iii) Give every table a number (Table 1, Table 2, etc.) and a self-explanatory caption; (iv) Refer to the table number at the appropriate place in the text (this will help the editor or layout designer to decide where to place the table when your paper is published).

When preparing figures (graphs, drawings, photographs, maps): (i) Consider what size they will be in the final publication and ensure the text and symbols will be clearly legible; (ii) Avoid using cluttered maps or graphs that are hard to read, especially 3-D graphs; (iii) Avoid using colour because the readers may wish to print pages using a black-and-white printer or photocopier; (iv) For all types of graphs, plot the independent variable on the horizontal x axis and the dependent variable on the vertical y axis, and label both axes, including units of measurement; (v) Most journals will not publish photographs of a study species or site unless they are an important part of the evidence (e.g. a rare species photographed with a camera trap); (vi) Give every figure a number (Fig. 1, Fig. 2, etc.) and a self-explanatory caption; (vii) Refer to the figure number in the text.

Most journals, including the *Cambodian Journal of Natural History*, require tables and figures to be submitted at the end of the manuscript or on separate files.

Discussion

The function of this section is to interpret your findings and explain what they mean for the understanding of this topic. What is obvious to you may not be obvious to all your readers, so try to spell this out clearly. You can assume your readers are intelligent but probably not experts on the subjects covered by your paper.

The first paragraph should begin with a brief summary of the main findings in two or three sentences, or a short paragraph. If the purpose of your study was to test a hypothesis or solve a particular problem, refer to this in the first paragraph.

The second and later paragraphs should contain a discussion and comparison of your research and findings with previous studies and/or work that has been carried out in similar areas. For example, if you have compiled a checklist of the birds of Kirirom National Park, compare your findings with inventories of birds in other protected areas in Cambodia, and attempt to explain any similarities or differences. Here, you may also discuss gaps or shortcomings in your own study, but keep this brief.

You may, if you wish, include speculation (opinions based on incomplete evidence) in the Discussion as long as it is clear you are speculating. For example, "We suspect that many of the large mammals move from high elevations to lower elevations during the dry season, but the data from this study are insufficient to confirm this".

The final paragraph(s) should discuss what happens next. For example, are there any management implications from your study? Do you have any recommendations; e.g. further research, new policies or other actions that should be taken? This last paragraph can also focus on the wider implications of your work, setting it into a broader context. Avoid ending your paper with the tired cliché that "more studies should be done". If you believe more research is necessary, explain why, and be very specific about what type of study is needed.

Unless it is required by the journal, there is no need to add a section entitled Conclusions. Instead, put any concluding remarks in the final paragraph of the Discussion.

Acknowledgements

This is the place to publicly, but briefly, thank the authorities that gave permission for the work to be carried out. You can also thank donors, assistants, people who have commented on the article, participating communities and any other individuals or organisations who have facilitated the work. One paragraph will do. There is no need to thank all of your friends, relatives and pets!

References

In alphabetical order, give full details of every reference that has been cited in your paper (including sources cited in your tables, figures and annexes, if any).

The best way to create a complete and tidy reference section is to use a bibliography manager. This will keep track of your citations and link them automatically to the reference section and thus ensure that all citations have matching references. Most bibliography managers contain a range of styles to suit most journals. There are several suitable pieces of software available, but we recommend Zotero, which is freely available for all computing platforms from <http://www.zotero.org/>

Your manuscript is now almost ready for submission. Check the journal's Instructions for Contributors one last time to make sure that you have prepared it correctly. For example, most journals (including the *Cambodian Journal of Natural History*) require the text to be double-spaced, to give the reviewers and editors room to write their comments by hand.

If the editors are satisfied that your manuscript meets the journal's criteria, they will forward it in confidence to a number of experts in the same field. These peer reviewers are asked to evaluate whether the work is genuinely original and of sufficient quality to be published, and to advise on whether any changes ought to be made. Peer-reviewing is a free service carried out by tens of thousands of scientists worldwide on the understanding that when they submit their manuscripts to journals their work will be reviewed in the same way, without payment.

Do not be disheartened if the comments from reviewers appear critical. This is normal, even for the most accomplished scientists. Reviewers often concentrate so intently on finding even the smallest errors that they forget to praise what they like about the work! Most of their advice will in fact be sensible and fair, so try to heed as much as you can—but never be afraid to tell the editor if you strongly disagree with any point. It is your name on the paper after all.

Having successfully passed careful scrutiny and corrected any mistakes, it is a proud moment when you see your work in print. On behalf of scientists, conservationists and natural resource managers everywhere, we applaud you for it. All too often, hard-earned data and insights remain hidden in notebooks or consigned to donor reports that are seen by only a handful of people. By sharing precious knowledge, experiences and opinions in open-access journals, all of us can gain a better understanding of this remarkable world. More importantly, your work will help your fellow scientists, sponsors and managers decide what needs to be done next.